

AUSTRALIAN
ACCESS FEDERATION

Experts in
Trust & Identity

15
YEARS

2025 Annual Plan

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Our strategic goals

Our Goal

We are **transforming** Australia's research, teaching and learning communities by **delivering innovative solutions** that **provide secure access** to **high-value digital resources and infrastructure**.

Our Guiding Principles

Our trust and identity solutions are **co-designed** by a **nationally engaged expert team using international best practice**. Our services are underpinned by **sustainable** business operations.

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Trust & Identity**

**Deliver
innovative
solutions**

**Build and
maintain a
culture of
excellence**

**Deliver
outstanding
customer
value**

**Enhance
operational
excellence**

Deliver innovative solutions

Major activities	2025 focus
<p>Drive the system-wide adoption of Trust and Identity within the NCRIS community</p> <p>Deliver the National PIDs Strategy in partnership with key contributors</p> <p>Develop new solutions and products that support our stakeholder's emerging Trust and Identity needs</p> <p>Implement Trust and Identity policy and technology aligned with international standards</p> <p>Lead and influence the national and international agenda for Trust and Identity</p>	<p>Expand AAF's market coverage and adapt products to support emerging research stakeholder needs</p> <hr/> <p>Measures of success:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Published T&I products and services roadmap reflecting known customer needs.<hr/>2. Secure new customers, particularly in underrepresented segments.<hr/>3. Customer retention and renewal.<hr/>4. Funding is awarded through the NDRI Strategy Investment Plan to support the T&I products and service roadmap delivery.<hr/>

Deliver outstanding customer value

Major activities	2025 focus
<p>Co-design Trust and Identity solutions with partners</p> <p>Continuously improve service and support delivery</p> <p>Promote AAF services and capabilities to stakeholders</p> <p>Increase the reach of AAF's services to all Australian researchers (government, industry, and citizen scientists)</p>	<p>AAF strengthens its relationship as a trusted sector partner</p> <hr/> <p>Measures of success:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. All NCRIS partner projects are delivered on time and budget. <hr/> <ol style="list-style-type: none">2. Annual focus groups report a positive sentiment towards AAF's value. <hr/> <ol style="list-style-type: none">3. 7 subscribers commit to migrating their on-premise identity provider to Rapid IdP. <hr/>

Build and maintain a culture of excellence

Major activities	2025 focus
<p>Nurture a collaborative and cohesive national team that is committed to excellence</p> <p>Recruit and retain the best people</p> <p>Encourage and support staff to improve their skills and develop in new areas of value to the AAF</p> <p>Effectively manage organisational change to support the achievement of the AAF's strategy</p>	<p>Create the foundations for a performance-based culture</p> <hr/> <p>Measures of success:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The top 3 priority areas from the staff engagement survey show improvement from the 2025 baseline. <hr/> <ol style="list-style-type: none">2. AAF evaluates staff sentiment about how well organisational changes are managed and uses feedback to improve subsequent change processes. <hr/>

Enhance operational excellence

Major activities	2025 focus
<p>Improve processes and implement tools to support business growth</p> <p>Continue to mature the AAF's cyber security posture</p> <p>Ensure the AAF remains financially sustainable</p> <p>Grow and diversify funding sources</p>	<p>Build capacity and resilience to support a growing organisation</p> <hr/> <p>Measures of success:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The transition to the new information management environment is complete and staff can effectively locate, manage and share information.<hr/>2. Processes and reporting are consistent across external and internal projects through the Project Management Office.<hr/>3. Dashboards and consistent periodic reporting are in place that streamline annual report production, customer roadshows, and Board reporting.<hr/>4. Any high-risk findings identified in the HR partner benchmark/baseline are adequately addressed/mitigated.<hr/>5. Any critical and high rated findings from external security reviews are quickly remediated and are verified as resolved in the follow-up assessment.<hr/>

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